

Analysis of Electric Vehicle Charging Networks

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Abstract—The expansion of electric vehicle (EV) charging station networks introduces new challenges related to the organization and efficiency of these infrastructures. A key concern in this context is ensuring that the network is well distributed, avoiding failures that could compromise the overall functioning of the system. In this regard, structural analysis of these networks becomes essential for identifying potential limitations and opportunities for improvement.

To address this, the present work proposes the modeling of a charging station network using graph theory, where stations are represented as nodes and connections between them as edges. Connections to the energy distributor are also considered, along with the assignment of weights to the edges, representing distances or costs.

Based on this modeling, a simulation was carried out in Python with the aim of analyzing network connectivity, identifying potential critical points, and evaluating the system's level of redundancy. The goal is to better understand the behavior of the network and its impacts in terms of efficiency and reliability.

This work contributes to the analysis of energy distribution systems in charging networks, offering a simple and efficient approach to identifying areas for improvement and supporting the planning of more robust infrastructures.

Index Terms—Graphs; Charging Networks; Connectivity; Analysis; Python

I. INTRODUCTION

The global transition to sustainable mobility has moved beyond a future promise to become a present reality in modern energy matrices, including the Brazilian scenario (Leão, 2024). However, the rapid expansion of electric vehicle (EV) fleets brings with it a critical challenge: supporting infrastructure. It is not enough to simply install chargers; it is necessary to ensure that this supply network is resilient, efficient, and capable of supporting demand without compromising the stability of the electrical system (Fernandes Orfo Júnior & Issao Hara, 2023).

In this context, structural analysis of charging networks becomes essential for anticipating failures and identifying optimization opportunities. A major current obstacle lies in the logical organization of these stations. A poorly distributed network can generate charging “blind spots” or overload specific nodes in the energy distribution network (Boçon, 2019). To address this complexity, Graph Theory emerges as a powerful mathematical tool, enabling the modeling of complex systems intuitively, where each station is treated as a node and connecting routes as edges (Darui, 2025).

This work proposes the modeling and structural analysis of charging networks using graph theory, focusing on connectivity, identification of critical points, and evaluation of system redundancy through computational simulation in Python. The central objective is to understand how network topology influences reliability, identifying critical elements that, if they were to fail, could isolate parts of the system or drastically reduce its operational efficiency.

II. METHODS

To analyze the structure of a charging station network, the project uses a model based on graph theory, in which stations are represented as nodes and connections between them as edges. Connections to the energy distributor were also considered, allowing for a more realistic representation of the system's operation.

The model also includes the assignment of weights to edges, representing distances or costs between stations, enabling the evaluation of the efficiency of existing connections in the network.

For system analysis, a simulation was carried out in a computational environment using the Python language, where the graph was constructed and evaluated based on criteria such as the number of connections per node and the distribution of links. This approach allowed for observation of network behavior and the identification of relevant characteristics related to its organization.

From this modeling, it was possible to analyze system connectivity, as well as to investigate the existence of potential critical points and the level of redundancy present in the network.

Thus, the adopted method enables a structured analysis of the network, contributing to the understanding of its performance and limitations.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the network modeling using graph theory (Figure 1), it was possible to represent charging stations as nodes and connections between them as edges, including connections to the energy distributor, based on synthetic data.

Source: Authors

Graph analysis allowed for the identification of important characteristics of the system, particularly regarding connectivity and critical points in the network.

Fig. 1. Modeling of a charging network based on graphs.

One of the main results was the identification of node N9 as a critical element of the network. This node has a high number of connections and is positioned centrally, being responsible for interconnecting different regions of the system. Due to these characteristics, a potential failure of this node could significantly compromise network operation, potentially causing station isolation, increased distances between points, and a reduction in overall efficiency.

Regarding the distributor (DIST), it was observed that it is not directly connected to all nodes, but rather to specific points in the network. This characterizes a hierarchical structure of energy distribution, which is consistent with real systems. However, this configuration may also generate some dependence on specific paths.

Another observed point was the presence of multiple connections between nodes, indicating that the network does not have a purely radial structure. This characteristic suggests the existence of redundancy, which contributes to greater system robustness in cases of isolated failures.

Furthermore, the weights assigned to edges represent the distances or costs between stations. Analysis of these values shows that shorter connections tend to be more efficient, while longer connections may increase the network's operational cost.

Overall, the results indicate that, although the network presents a satisfactory level of connectivity and redundancy, there are still areas for improvement. The strong dependence on node N9 and the limitation of paths linked to the distributor indicate the need for better distribution of connections.

Possible improvements include the creation of alternative paths between nodes, the reduction of dependence on critical points, and a more balanced distribution of network load.

Thus, the analysis demonstrates that the system is functional but can be optimized to increase its reliability and efficiency

in real-world applications.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The development of the charging station network analysis using graph theory enabled a clearer understanding of the system's organization and operation. Through modeling and Python-based simulation, it was possible to represent the connections between points and evaluate important network characteristics.

During the analysis, relevant aspects were identified, such as connectivity between nodes, the presence of redundancy, and the existence of more critical points within the structure. These factors are important as they directly influence the performance and reliability of the system as a whole.

Although the network presents adequate operation and a degree of robustness due to multiple connections, limitations were also observed, such as dependence on certain nodes and the concentration of connections at specific points. These characteristics indicate that, in failure scenarios, parts of the network may be impacted.

Overall, the work achieved its objective by enabling structural analysis of the network, providing a more detailed view of its behavior. Furthermore, the results obtained indicate that the system can be improved through the creation of new connections and a more balanced distribution of links.

In summary, the use of graph theory combined with computational simulation proved to be an efficient approach for studying this type of system, contributing to the identification of areas for improvement and to the development of more reliable solutions in real-world applications.

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